

Research Paper

Godfatherism and Political Conflict in Rivers State: Implications for State Development

By

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ABSTRACT: The study investigated Godfatherism and Political Conflict with emphasis on its Implications for Development in Rivers State. In a political environment dominated by godfatherism, public funds are often used to maintain political loyalty and settle patronage networks. Resources that should support long-term developments are redirected to reward loyal supporters, strengthen political alliances, and secure elite control. This weakens investment in critical sectors and limits the benefits that ordinary citizens derive from the state's wealth. The objectives of the study were to examine the politics of Rivers State between 1999 and 2023, and analyse the impact of godfatherism on accountability, competence, good governance and development of River State. The study adopted the Elite Theory propounded by Robert Michel, Gaetano Mosca and Vilfredo Pareto. The study utilised a descriptive research design and relied on secondary sources of data; data were sourced from academic journals, books, theses, government publications, policy documents, credible newspapers, official statements, and reports from electoral bodies and civil society organisations. The study concluded that godfatherism continues to hinder accountability, effective leadership, good governance and development in Rivers State. This system weakens democracy, ignores the voices of ordinary citizens, and slows development by putting the interests of a few powerful elites above the needs of the people. The study recommends, amongst others, electoral reforms and conscious efforts to reduce the cost of contesting elections as panacea for mitigating the influence of godfatherism in Nigeria's political landscape. This can be achieved by strengthening INEC, introducing technological innovations, encouraging internal party democracy, and ensuring judicial integrity. With this, the perception that all one needs is a godfather to be declared the winner of an election will diminish, and focus will shift to service, competence, and genuine public interest.

Keywords: Godfatherism, political conflict, accountability, good governance, development

I. Introduction

Philosophers of politics have long recognised the fact that politics is an important aspect of human existence. It is ubiquitous, and one cannot do without it even at the micro level. Politics represents the noblest activity, which the ancient philosophers prized among other things as a duty for the citizen to get involved in the affairs of the *polis*. Plato sees politics as an activity that should be left in the hands of the philosopher rulers because they possess inherent qualities and knowledge about leadership, which he terms the knowledge of the good. These men, philosopher rulers, are just; they are not concerned about material things and have incisive minds to make just laws for the good of society generally. Aristotle reminds us of the nature of man as a political animal. Implying that, it is only at the level of activities of the state that one finds self-sufficiency, as he cooperates with other humans in making decisions about their everyday lives. Hence, both philosophers recognised that the essence of politics is to inculcate values in the individual to be a good citizen and have the highest level of loyalty to the constitutional state. Politics is the process of resolving conflicts that arise inherently from the economy (Ndu, 2005). Wherever man is found, he is seen in group and because the bounties of nature are not sufficient to meet the needs of all in society, there is

usually a struggle in the distribution of these bounties. Politics, therefore, is intended to create mechanisms to ensure peace, justice, harmony and fairness in the distribution of resources in society. The process that leads to the peaceful resolution of the crisis that arises in society is called politics. Politics is the process by which groups of people make decisions and the activities associated with the governance of a country or area. It involves the distribution of power and resources, the creation and enforcement of laws and the regulation of social relationships. The conception of politics varies from one scholar to another; also, the manner in which politics is practised (played) varies from one country to another. While in liberal societies such as the United Kingdom, the United States of America, and Canada, etc., have always applied the rules (based on the laid down procedures and constitution), that is not the case in most developing countries and Nigeria in particular. This has far reaching implication for the quality of our democracy and, by extension, socio-economic and political development. The political arena in Nigeria and Rivers state in particular is mired with thuggery, assassination, voter intimidation, imposition and godfatherism, etc. Godfatherism is used to describe a system where a powerful individual (the godfather) uses their influence, wealth, and resources to support and install political candidates (the godsons) into positions of power (Eyo, 2012). This relationship often implies that the godsons owe their loyalty and political decisions to the godfathers, who in return expect certain favours or control over political and economic decisions. Godfatherism often involves a 'patron-client relationship' where the godfather sponsors the godson to a position of authority, and in return, the godson is expected to do the bidding of the godfather.

Godfatherism has grave implications for accountability, competence, good governance and overall development; in most cases, the candidate the godfather imposes on the people may not be competent and rather than being accountable to the people, such a candidate owes his/her allegiance to the godfather who facilitates his/her elections. Thus, resources (common patrimony) that are meant to uplift the well-being of the people are deployed to service the godfather, thereby denying the people the dividends of democracy. The situation is so worrisome in Nigeria and Rivers state in particular, as political elites aspiring for positions of authority rely on the support and endorsements of godfathers, rather than reaching out to the people to sell their manifesto and programmes.

II. Statement of the Problem

The politics of godfatherism has been the focal point of party politics in developing countries around the globe, and it has remained one of the greatest glitches facing the Nigerian political system since the return of the country to democratic rule in 1999. Although party politics is not an unfamiliar phenomenon in Nigerian political history, the country has seen an increase in it since returning to democratic rule in 1999. The menace of godfatherism and its practice has not only retarded the process of democratic consolidation in Nigeria but has also undermined effective State governance and restricted rather than broadened democratic representation.

Annie (2013) noted that godfatherism in Nigerian politics has eaten deep into the country's political space and economy. It has led to political slavery, puppetry leadership, dogmatic citizenship, and denies peaceful coexistence, law and order, and all the tenets of the democratic process in the country. It has become a threatening phenomenon in Nigerian politics and the democratisation process, and has remained amongst the most dangerous challenges to democracy today. In other words, godfatherism has had far-reaching, dire consequences for Nigeria's democratization process. It has a profound impact on society, leading to a lack of accountability, pervasive corruption and economic mismanagement, etc. The scenario painted above is not different from what is obtainable in Rivers state. The State was among the twelve States created in 1967. Since the return to democratic rule in 1999, the decision of who gets what, when and how, as regards occupation of the position of authority in the State, is often decided by godfathers. Former governor of Rivers state, Sir Dr Peter Odili rule from 1999-2007 and before the conduct of the 2007 general elections, the decision of who would succeed Odili was a major issue for the then ruling party (Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) and the political class. While the primary elections conducted by the PDP produced the then speaker of Rivers State House of Assembly, Hon. Rotimi Amaechi, former President Obasanjo decided to hand over the flag of the party to Celestine Omehia. This necessitated a legal tussle as Amaechi later reclaimed his mandate at the Supreme Court. By 2015, Amaechi had completed his tenure, and the baton of leadership was to be handed over to a new successor, which polarised the political elite in the state due to their divergent interests. The internal dynamics within the PDP compelled the then governor Rotimi Amaechi to defect to the newly formed All Progressive Congress (APC), leaving the structure of the PDP to the former Minister of State for Education, Barr. Nyesom Wike. Wike emerged as the governor of the

state owing to his attachment to the Federal government. In the 2023 general election, although contested by numerous parties, the PDP was the party to beat owing to the support of the outgoing Governor, Barr. Nyesom Wike gave to his candidates, who, after the 2023 general elections, Governor Sir Siminalayi Fubara emerged the winner of the PDP flag and became the sitting Governor of Rivers State, and is currently serving, which did not bring peace and tranquillity between his godfather and himself to date. The effects of entrenched patron–client politics are especially serious in Rivers State because of the state’s strong economic position in Nigeria. Rivers State is one of the leading oil-producing states in the country and hosts major multinational oil and gas companies such as Shell Nigeria and Nigeria LNG. As a result, the state receives large revenues from oil production as well as substantial internally generated revenue. These financial resources should ordinarily be used to improve infrastructure, education, healthcare, job creation, and environmental protection in oil-producing communities. However, in a political environment dominated by godfatherism, these public funds are often used to maintain political loyalty and settle patronage networks. Resources that should support long-term development are redirected to reward loyal supporters, strengthen political alliances, and secure elite control. This weakens investment in critical sectors and limits the benefits that ordinary citizens derive from the state’s wealth. The major issue is the crack between Rivers State’s huge economic potential and its repeated political instability caused by godfatherism. Despite the state’s wealth, political conflicts between godfathers and their protégés frequently disrupt governance. These power struggles interfere with policy implementation, delay development projects, and create uncertainty within state institutions. As a result, there is poor policy continuity, reduced public confidence in democratic institutions, and administrative inefficiency during periods of crisis. In addition, when political appointments and leadership positions are based on loyalty rather than merit, competent individuals are sidelined. This weakens the civil service, reduces accountability, and slows sustainable development in the state.

Earlier studies have examined godfatherism in Nigeria from a wider national perspective. For example, Albert (2005) studied political godfatherism in the Fourth Republic, focusing on the crisis in Anambra State, and showed how conflicts between political patrons and their protégés destabilised governance and electoral processes. Similarly, Ayoade (2006) examined godfather politics and its effects on democratic governance in Nigeria, concluding that it promotes corruption and weakens institutional accountability. While these studies provide useful insights, they mainly discuss the issue at a general national level or concentrate on isolated political crises. They do not deeply connect godfatherism to long-term development outcomes at the state level. This present study is different because it specifically examines the politics of Rivers State from 1999 to 2023 and carefully analyses how godfatherism has affected accountability, leadership competence, good governance and overall development of the state.

III. Objectives of the Study

The study is guided by the following objectives:

1. Examine the politics of Rivers State between 1999 and 2023.
2. Analyse the impact of godfatherism on accountability, competence, good governance and development of River State.

IV. Literature Review

Concept of Godfatherism

The term “godfather” appears in many Western political studies, often used to describe powerful individuals who influence political decisions behind the scenes. However, as Dickson (2012) explains, the concept takes on a deeper and more culturally rooted meaning in Nigeria. In the Nigerian context, godfatherism is closely linked to long-standing patron–client relationships that have existed among major ethnic groups such as the Hausa, Yoruba, and Igbo. The idea of attaching oneself to a powerful and resourceful individual for protection, support, or advancement is not new in these societies. In fact, local terms that reflect the idea of a “godfather” have existed since the pre-colonial period. Among the Hausa, the godfather figure is commonly referred to as “maigida,” which literally means landlord or head of a household. According to Jude (2009), the term goes beyond its literal meaning. Scholars such as Abner

Cohen, Paul Lovejoy, and Polly Hill used it to describe individuals who acted as brokers for Hausa traders operating across West Africa. These traders transported cattle from the North to southern regions and returned with kola nuts. During their journeys, they depended on the maigida at various transit centres for accommodation, storage, and assistance in conducting business. In return, the maigida received compensation and often became wealthy due to the number of clients under his care. Even within Hausaland, such patron–client relationships were common. As Ferguson (2010) observed, when a trader and a buyer lodged in different houses, both landlords received symbolic gifts during transactions, reinforcing the culture of patronage and mutual benefit.

In Yorubaland, Bash (2013) notes that a godfather may be described as “baba kekere” (small father), “baba isale” (father of the underground), or “baba nigbejo” (a reliable helper in times of trouble). The most historically significant of these is “baba kekere.” In the nineteenth century, Yoruba migrants who settled in Ibadan often attached themselves to powerful chiefs known as baba kekere. These chiefs were appointed by the Ibadan traditional council to oversee specific communities. Migrants paid tribute to them, and in return, the chiefs offered protection and social security in a period marked by instability and violence. The relationship was based on loyalty and mutual obligation. In Igbo society, Dayo (2012) traces the roots of godfatherism to the traditional apprenticeship system, particularly the relationship between “Nnam-Ukwu” (master) and “Odibo” (servant or apprentice). In this system, a young person was placed under the guidance of a more experienced individual for training in business and moral discipline. After completing the training, the master was expected to support the apprentice in establishing his own enterprise. This relationship was built on mentorship, trust, and eventual empowerment.

Across these three cultural contexts, a common pattern emerges: individuals of lower status align themselves with more powerful figures for social and economic advancement. In return, the patron receives loyalty, respect, or material benefits. While such arrangements were traditionally accepted and regulated by social norms, the problem arises when this system is transferred into modern politics. Gbemiga (2009) argues that contemporary godfatherism represents a distortion of these traditional practices. What was once a system of mentorship and protection has evolved into a political arrangement driven by excessive demands and personal enrichment. The modern political godfather often expects substantial financial returns and political control in exchange for support. This shift has had serious negative consequences for Nigeria’s democratic development.

Historically, elements of godfatherism were present even in the early formation of party politics in Nigeria. According to Gbemiga (2009), the first generation of Nigerian elites who interacted with European colonial authorities acted as intermediaries between colonial officials and local communities. Traditional rulers played central roles under the British indirect rule system. Educated elites, religious leaders, and business figures also functioned as gatekeepers who controlled access to colonial administrators and European trading firms. Individuals who lacked formal education relied on letter writers and petitioners to present their cases. Some early nationalists, including Chief Obafemi Awolowo, invested in business ventures such as transportation and later entered politics. These early elites determined who could access colonial power structures, thereby acting as informal political patrons.

Jibrim (2011) notes that political godfatherism became more visible during the nationalist movements of the 1950s. At that time, the educated elite, though small in number, led the struggle for independence. They were respected for their courage and knowledge and became influential leaders within their regions. Major political parties such as the Northern People’s Congress (NPC), the Action Group (AG), and the National Council of Nigerian Citizens (NCNC) were led by dominant regional figures. Leaders such as Sir Ahmadu Bello, Chief Obafemi Awolowo, and Dr Nnamdi Azikiwe played decisive roles in shaping political opportunities within their regions. According to Olu (2008), these early political godfathers acted as mentors and ideological leaders. They emphasised development, discipline, and accountability rather than personal financial gain.

The key difference between earlier and contemporary godfatherism lies in motivation and conduct. The earlier generation focused largely on political ideology, regional development, and leadership grooming. They supported their protégés with guidance and logistical backing without demanding excessive personal rewards. In contrast, many modern godfathers prioritise financial returns and political dominance. Olu (2008) observes that some later politicians who claimed allegiance to the ideals of leaders like Awolowo

failed to uphold their principles, contributing to political decline in subsequent democratic periods. The commercialisation of politics during the military regimes of General Ibrahim Babangida and General Sani Abacha further strengthened contemporary godfatherism. According to Audu (2004), politics during these periods became heavily monetised, and loyalty to those in power was rewarded with financial and political advantages. Individuals who supported the regimes built extensive patronage networks and accumulated wealth. When Nigeria returned to civilian rule in 1999, many of these individuals transitioned into democratic politics, using their financial resources and networks to dominate party structures and electoral processes. By the 2023 elections, godfatherism had become deeply entrenched in party politics across Nigeria. Party conventions were characterised by intense financial competition, where the strength of a candidate often depended on the financial capacity and influence of his or her political sponsor. Ordinary citizens had limited influence in determining candidates, as party nominations were largely controlled by powerful patrons. Since then, political godfathers have continued to consolidate their influence, shaping electoral outcomes and governance processes in many parts of the country.

Concept of Political Conflicts

Before delving into conceptualising political conflict, it is paramount to first understand the meaning of conflict. Conflict as a concept is not new in the field of international relations and diplomacy, as it has almost become a daily occurrence across states, regions and organisations. Conflict is so important that several departments in universities, institutes and research centres have been set up to conduct studies on why it occurs, its impacts on society and the possible ways to prevent it. Notwithstanding the importance, there has not been a universally accepted definition of the concept. Wani (2011), for instance, posits that conflict is a term used to mean a variety of things like serious disagreements, incompatibilities, fight, argument, contest, combat, clash and war. Similarly, Udeso (2018) notes that originally, conflict used to mean strike at another fight with an enemy or to do battle with an opposing force and that today it also means to be antagonistic towards others or to be in sharp disagreement with others. Political conflict can be understood as disputes or confrontations that arise when individuals, groups, or institutions within a political system pursue opposing or incompatible goals. Such conflicts may revolve around who holds power, how public resources are shared, who controls state institutions, or how laws and policies are interpreted and implemented. Conflict is a normal feature of political life in both democratic and non-democratic systems. Scholars generally distinguish between constructive conflict, which encourages dialogue, reform, and broader participation, and destructive conflict, which results in instability, violence, and the weakening of institutions (Dahl, 1971; Easton, 1965).

In Nigeria, political conflict is deeply rooted in the country's historical and structural realities, including colonial legacies, ethnic diversity, military rule, and disputes over resource allocation. Nigeria's large population and its complex mix of ethnic and religious identities have made political competition persistent and, at times, intense (Suberu, 2001). Since gaining independence in 1960, the country has experienced different forms of political conflict, such as election-related violence, ethnic clashes, separatist movements, and confrontations between government authorities and organised groups (Adebayo & Aluko, 2016).

A major cause of contemporary political conflict in Nigeria is the contest for political power and access to state resources. Because political office often provides control over economic benefits, competition among elites and ethnic groups has become highly intense. Nigeria's federal system, particularly the management of oil and gas resources, has increased rivalry among regions and political actors seeking influence over revenue flows (Agbaje & Adejumbi, 2006). Tensions tend to escalate when elections or political decisions are perceived as unfair, manipulated, or exclusionary (Omotola, 2010).

Economic hardship further fuels political conflict in the country. High levels of unemployment, poverty, and inequality have generated widespread dissatisfaction with political leadership. When citizens feel excluded from economic opportunities and decision-making processes, frustration can translate into agitation and unrest (Obi & Rustad, 2011). The conflict in the Niger Delta, for instance, was partly driven by the belief that oil wealth benefited the federal government and multinational corporations while host communities remained underdeveloped and environmentally degraded (Okonta & Douglas, 2003).

V. Theoretical Framework

Elite Theory

The theory adopted for this study is the Elite Theory propounded by Robert Michel, Gaetano Mosca and Vilfredo Pareto. In the view of Michel (1915), the ultimate fate of all organisations is to be run by a small minority or plural elites. In the view of Mosca (1939), human societies are divided into two major classes of people, namely, the rulers and the ruled. The ruling class is a minority group who monopolize power and enjoys the advantages that accrue from it. The ruled class (masses), on the other hand, constitute the majority group but are directed and left in the hands of subsistence by the ruling class. Mosca (1939) went further to assert that power is always in the hands of an organised minority who have authority and power over the majority by virtue of certain characteristics such as consensus based on forms, cohesiveness and consciousness. A situation described as the iron law of oligarchy. The theory posits that power in the state or any organisation is exercised by a limited number of individuals or groups referred to as elites. The theory, therefore, views society as closed, pyramidal and unresponsive and composed of the few who rule and the many who are ruled. The dominant argument is that the large mass of the people are ignoble, not cohesive and not organised, and so are not competent or capable of exercising political power. Applying the Elite's Theory in understanding godfatherism, it becomes paramount to state that the political elite feel they know it all, and they are in a position to dictate to the masses. They often impose candidates on the people without looking at the capability of the candidate to meet the yearnings and aspirations of the people. They feel they know it all, and the masses lack understanding of the system. The top-down approach (imposition) rather than bottom top approach (consultation) is the bane of Nigeria's socio-economic development.

VI. Empirical Review

Ejumudo and Ogbe (2025) carried out a study titled *Godfatherism and Political Conflict in Nigeria: A Study of Rivers State, Nigeria*, examined godfatherism and political conflict in Nigeria, with a specific focus on Rivers State. A comprehensive background to the study was presented alongside other relevant issues. Three research hypotheses were formulated in line with the stated objectives to guide the investigation. Relevant literature was reviewed, reflecting the positions of various scholars on the key sub-themes of the study. Both conceptual and empirical literature were consulted, with emphasis on godfatherism and political conflict. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design, implemented through the use of a questionnaire as the primary research instrument. A sample size of 400 respondents was drawn from the study population using a simple random sampling technique. Descriptive data were analysed using frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores, while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Coorelation. The findings revealed that godfatherism contributes significantly to political conflict in Rivers State, as it undermines political stability, democratic values, and the political leadership structure. The study recommended, among other measures, that godfatherism should be discouraged through attitudinal reorientation and the enactment and enforcement of relevant legislation to prevent powerful political actors from hijacking political structures and processes in the state. The study further emphasised that constitutional provisions should form the foundation for democratic practice, particularly in matters relating to political leadership in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Ojong et al. (2025) carried out a study titled *Godfatherism and Favouritism on Political Appointments in Cross River State: Implications for Grassroots Development*. The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a population of 1,527,289 registered voters in the 2023 general elections. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample of 400 respondents was drawn across the three senatorial districts of the state (North, Central, and South) through stratified random sampling. A structured questionnaire on a four-point Likert scale served as the primary instrument for data collection. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) for the research questions, while one-sample t-test and ANOVA were employed to test three hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. Results revealed that godfatherism significantly influences political appointments in Cross River State ($t(398) = 5.42, p < 0.05$), and that favouritism negatively affects grassroots development ($t(398) = 6.87, p < 0.05$). Furthermore, there was a significant difference across senatorial districts in the extent to which political patronage impacts grassroots development ($F(2, 397) = 4.16, p < 0.05$), with the South showing the strongest negative effects. Although a few responses indicated occasional merit-based appointments, the overwhelming evidence

confirmed the dominance of patronage politics in the State. The study concluded that godfatherism and favouritism remain critical impediments to democratic governance and grassroots development in Cross River State. It recommended institutional reforms to promote merit-based appointments, civic education to discourage patronage politics, and equitable distribution of appointments across senatorial districts to strengthen democratic institutions and grassroots participation.

VII. Materials and Methods

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The design was considered suitable because it enabled the researcher to systematically describe and explain the patterns, nature, and effects of godfatherism in the state's political environment between 1999 and 2023. The study relied on secondary sources of data, including academic journals, textbooks, theses, government publications, policy documents, credible newspapers, official statements, and reports from electoral bodies and civil society organisations. These sources were appropriate because the research focused on historical political developments, electoral transitions, and documented crises that had already been reported and analysed. The use of secondary data also enabled the researcher to engage with existing scholarly debates on godfatherism, political conflict, accountability, and governance in Nigeria, while situating the experience of Rivers State within the broader national context. The data collected were analysed using qualitative content analysis. This method involved examining relevant documents and texts to identify key themes, patterns, and relationships related to patronage politics, elite rivalry, political succession, and governance performance.

VIII. Results and Discussion

Politics of Rivers State between 1999 and 2023

Rivers State is one of the thirty-six states in Nigeria that has been under democratic rule since Nigeria returned to democracy in 1999. The state is endowed with mineral resources such as crude oil and contributes greatly to the economy of the country. The state is unique in terms of ethnic configuration as there are over seven ethnic groups that make up the state, the major ethnic groups are: Ikwerre, Ogoni and Ijaw. Other minorities ethnic groups in the state are: Ekpeye, Etche and Abua, etc. The state has three senatorial district such as Rivers East, Rivers South East and Rivers West. Below is a table that depicts the three senatorial districts in Rivers State.

Table 1: Local Government Area in the three Senatorial Districts in Rivers State

Rivers East	Rivers South-East	Rivers West
Port Harcourt	Opobo/Nkoro	Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni
Ikwerre	Andoni	Ahoda East
Okirika	Oyigbo	Abua/Odual
Ogu/Bolo	Tai	Degema
Obio/Akpor	Eleme	Akuku-Toro
Omuma	Khana	Asari-Toru
Etche	Gokana	Bonny
Emohua		

Source: Researcher's compilation (2023)

Table 1 above revealed the composition of the local government area on the basis of senatorial district. The table revealed that Rivers East has the highest number of local government areas, eight precisely, as against those of Rivers South East and Rivers West, which are seven respectively. The local governments in Rivers East are the largest in terms of land mass and population. Obio/Akpor local government area land mass and voting strength are by far those of Degema and Bonny Local government area when put together. This assertion is based on the 2023 governorship results in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, where the total number of votes cast was 63,299 compared to those of Degema and Bonny Local Government Area, 9,301 and 11,345 votes respectively (INEC, 2023).

The state is also divided into upland and riverine; upland is made up of ethnic groups in the upland area, such as Ogoni, Ikwerre and Etche, etc., while riverine is made up of ethnic groups in the riverine area, such as Ijaw. Political power is supposed to be shared or rotated based on the upland and riverine areas. In 1999, when Niger returned to democratic rule, Sir Peter Odili from Rivers West Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area, a riverine, emerged as the governor of the state. By 2007, Sir Odili handed over political power to the upland in the person of Hon. Rotimi Amaechi. Amaechi handed over political power to Nyesome Wike from the upland, and Wike handed over political power to Sir Simianalyi Fubara, the present governor, from the riverine. Below is a table that depicts the names of Governors Rivers State has produced since 1999.

Table 2: Names of Governors that ruled Rivers State since 1999 to date

S/N	Name	Year	Political Party	Upland/Riverine
1	Sir Peter Odili	May 1999- May 2007	Peoples Democratic Party (PDP)	Riverine
2	Hon. Rotimi Amaechi	Oct. 25 2007-May 29, 2015	354,366	Upland
3	Chief Barr. Nyesom Wike	May 29 2015-May 29 2023	Peoples Democratic Party (PDP)	Upland
4	Sir Siminalayi Fubara	May 29, 2023-till date	Peoples Democratic Party (PDP)	Riverine

Source: Researcher compilation (2023)

Table 2 above revealed the names of Governors Rivers State has produced since 1999, when Nigeria returned to democratic rule. It also revealed the political party under which these personalities governed the state.

One interesting scenario, like politics in Rivers State, especially since 1999 when Nigeria returned to democratic rule, is the influence of a political godfather in the scheme of things. Since 1999, when Dr Peter Odili became governor of Rivers State, to date, in the words of Ann, political godfatherism and the ongoing animosity amongst these figures, godfather and godsons, have caused constant political instability in the state (Ann, 2024). The perpetual fallout first started with Peter Odili and his political godfather, the late Marshal Harry. It will be recalled that Odili rose to power on the structures of the late Marshal Harry, who was his godfather, but when he became governor, Odili dismantled Harry's structures in an epic political battle, and this led to their parting ways (Ann, 2024). Odili later established his own structures. The second fallout between political godfathers and their godsons, as noted by Ann (2024), was between Peter Odili and his political godson Rotimi Amaechi. While Odili was preparing to exit office, he had narrowed his search for a successor to Amaechi, who was then the Speaker of the State House of Assembly. But when Amaechi emerged as the flag-bearer, his rise did not go down well with some Abuja 'bigwigs', and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) was sent after him, seizing all his travel documents. Following fruitless efforts to support Amaechi's ascent, Odili gave in to resistance to the ticket and chose Dr Celestine Omehia, Amaechi's cousin. Trampled and pursued, Amaechi fled to Ghana for a while and filed a lawsuit to overturn his disqualification (Nwambuko & Omiunu, 2024). He broke off communication with Odili and returned to exact revenge on his political mentor on October 25, 2007, when the court found in his favour. When Amaechi became governor on October 25, 2007, by the order of the Supreme Court, he dismantled Odili's political dynasty, probably due to the saga that bedevilled his emergence as the flag bearer of the People's Democratic Party (PDP) in 2006. The situation resulted in animosity between Omehia and Odili supporters on the part of Amaechi's camp, which ultimately caused a crisis that shattered the father-son political bond between the Odili and Amaechi (Nwambuko & Omiunu, 2024).

The third fallout between political godfathers and their godsons was between Amaechi and Nelson Wike. Wike, who held the position of Chief of Staff during Amaechi's first term from 2007 to 2011, was a staunch supporter of the governor. Their alliance, however, soured when Amaechi claimed to have noticed Wike's autocratic inclinations, named Mr Tony Okocha as his successor during his second term, and moved Wike to the centre, where he was named Minister of State for Education. Wike arrived in Abuja and began a scheme to destroy Amaechi's organisation, proving to be the worst political nightmare for the then-governor, who had calculated that shipping Wike to Abuja would destroy his nascent political career. After the altercation between the then-governor and then first lady, Patience Jonathan, he felt even more confident to challenge Amaechi. The political alliance between Wike and Amaechi ultimately broke down when Wike's allies took control of the state PDP executive structure from the Amaechi-supporting administration through dubious legal means (Nwambuko & Omiunu, 2024). In the end, Wike had complete control over the PDP's structure when Amaechi and a few of his men, including Magnus Abe, defected to the All-Progressives Congress (APC). Wike's emergence altered the political arrangement in terms of power sharing between the upland and the riverine, as Amaechi was from the upland and Wike was equally from the upland.

The recent fallout between political godfathers and their godsons is between Wike and his godson, Siminalaye Fubara. Prior to March 18, 2023 governorship election, about seven aspirants indicated interest in the race on the platform of PDP, including Felix Obuah, Isaac Kamalu and the current Secretary to the State Government, Tammy Danagogo and Siminanlaye Fubara, former accountant general of the state among others. Wike promised to return political power to riverine people, and as such, Fubara was backed by Wike, who emerged as the party's candidate, who eventually won the governorship election, all thanks to Wike (Nwambuko & Omiunu, 2024). However, it is not surprising that the relationship between the duo turned sour so quickly. Wike has been accused of overbearing influence in the state. For instance, almost all the cabinet members who serve in Wike's administration were retained in the Fubara administration. The party structure from the Ward, Local Government and State are under the grip of the Wike, further portraying the excessive control of the former Governor over the state. Wike, who had during the Presidential elections worked against his own party, the PDP, was rewarded with a Ministerial appointment (Minister of Federal Capital Territory) in the government of President Bola Tinubu. This further brought Wike to the corridor of power in the Presidency. It is this enormous power in the Presidency that Wike has deployed to wage war against his godson, the Governor of Rivers State.

Impact of Godfatherism on Accountability, Competence, Good Governance and Development of River State

The impact of godfatherism on accountability, competence, good governance, and development in Rivers State is profound and multidimensional. Accountability and competence are central pillars of democratic governance. In a functional democracy, elected representatives are expected to remain answerable to the electorate for the management of public resources and the implementation of policies. Candidates are ordinarily required to present clear manifestoes and policy programmes to the people, enabling voters to make informed choices based on competence, credibility, and vision. Through this process, leadership is expected to emerge from popular mandate and public scrutiny. However, the political reality in Nigeria, and particularly in Rivers State, has often departed from this democratic ideal. The processes of candidate selection and electoral competition are frequently influenced or controlled by political godfathers who determine who contests and who eventually occupies public office. Sakariyau (2013) observes that the political process in Nigeria is heavily regulated by elite interests, with numerous structural and financial barriers placed before aspirants. At party conventions, financial influence and elite endorsement often outweigh considerations of integrity, policy ideas, and competence. Aspirants are compelled to align themselves with powerful patrons to secure party nominations, and without such backing, their chances of success are significantly reduced.

In Rivers State, this pattern has shaped political recruitment since the return to democratic rule in 1999. The dominance of the People's Democratic Party (PDP) in the state's governorship elections reflects the influence of entrenched political actors who control party structures and determine succession outcomes. The emergence of Sir Siminalayi Fubara as the PDP governorship candidate, following the withdrawal of other aspirants, illustrates how elite consensus rather than competitive internal democracy often determines candidacy. In such situations, the electorate is largely excluded from meaningful participation in leadership

selection, as decisions are taken by a small circle of power brokers. The consequence of this system is weakened accountability. When a public office holder owes his political rise primarily to a godfather rather than to the electorate, his loyalty is redirected from the people to the political patron. Governance decisions are then influenced by the need to satisfy the demands and expectations of the godfather, sometimes at the expense of public interest. Public funds and state resources may be diverted to maintain patronage networks, reward loyalists, or consolidate elite influence. This undermines fiscal responsibility and reduces transparency in public administration. Competence is equally affected under a godfather-driven political arrangement. Candidate selection is often based on loyalty, personal allegiance, and perceived obedience rather than merit, experience, or administrative capacity. Individuals who demonstrate independence or strong reformist tendencies may be sidelined if they are perceived as unwilling to submit to elite control. As a result, the quality of leadership and bureaucratic performance declines, and governance becomes reactive rather than strategic. Policies may lack coherence and continuity, particularly when political conflicts emerge between godfathers and their protégés. The wider implications for good governance are significant. Political parties are essential institutions in democratic systems because they facilitate representation and participation (Adele, 2001; Agbaje, 2005). Democracy requires that citizens actively participate in the selection of leaders and that elected officials represent the interests of the wider community. However, when party structures are dominated by godfathers, internal democracy is weakened, and representation becomes skewed in favour of elite interests. Iboje (2009) argues that political elites often assume exclusive knowledge of what is best for society, marginalising the voices of ordinary citizens. In Rivers State, this elite-driven decision-making process has frequently alienated the masses from governance, reinforcing the perception that political power is controlled by a select few.

Ugwu and Ugwuja (2016) contend that godfatherism concentrates political power in the hands of a minority who function as kingmakers, thereby depriving citizens of their right to determine who governs them. This erosion of popular sovereignty fosters political apathy, as citizens lose confidence in the electoral process and the responsiveness of political leaders. When voters perceive that election outcomes are predetermined by elite negotiations, participation declines, and democratic legitimacy weakens. Godfatherism also generates instability when disagreements arise between godfathers and their protégés. Once a godson resists the influence of his patron or attempts to assert independence, political crises often ensue. Such conflicts disrupt governance, delay policy implementation, and divert attention from development priorities. Oghuvbu (2023) notes that the expansion of godfather politics since 1999 has slowed democratic consolidation and undermined effective state governance. Similarly, Eke and Edosa (2017) argue that the system fuels corruption, impunity, and underdevelopment by weakening institutional checks and balances. The developmental consequences for Rivers State are particularly severe given its economic importance as an oil-producing state. Instead of channelling substantial revenues toward infrastructure, healthcare, education, and employment generation, political actors may prioritise servicing patronage obligations. As Chimaroke Nnamani observed, the financial cost of satisfying godfathers places additional strain on limited state resources, thereby undermining development efforts. The diversion of resources toward elite settlements constrains the capacity of the state to meet the needs of the broader population.

IX. Conclusion

The study highlights that godfatherism continues to hinder accountability, effective leadership, good governance and development in Rivers State. This system weakens democracy, ignores the voices of ordinary citizens, and slows development by putting the interests of a few powerful elites above the needs of the people. For Rivers State to achieve lasting development and political stability, the power of godfathers must be limited, political processes made more open and fair, and leaders held truly accountable to the public rather than to private patrons. Only by promoting transparency, merit-based leadership, and active citizen participation can the state use its resources effectively for the benefit of all and strengthen democratic governance.

X. Recommendations

Based on the findings, the paper recommended the following:

1. Strengthening INEC: Nigeria's political institutions, particularly the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), should be strengthened to enhance their effectiveness and independence. Legal frameworks should be established or reinforced to prevent any form of interference in the Commission's operations, ensuring it functions without undue influence.
2. Technological Innovations: The use of biometric technology, the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS), and real-time electronic transmission of results reduces the susceptibility of the electoral umpire to pressure from powerful politicians.
3. Internal Party Democracy: Reforms emphasizing strict adherence to internal democracy prevent godfathers from imposing candidates, forcing them to adopt transparent, merit-based selection processes.
4. Campaign Finance Regulation: Strict enforcement of laws limiting campaign spending can break the cycle of dependency on godfathers,
5. Judicial Integrity: A robust, independent judiciary is essential to swiftly and impartially handle election disputes, ensuring that illegal godfather-driven results are overturned.

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